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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST IN PRIVATE COMPANIES: A COMPANY LAW PERSPECTIVE FROM UKRAINE AND SELECTED EUROPEAN JURISDICTIONS¹

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This paper examines how company law addresses conflicts of interest in private companies in Ukraine and three EU countries: Cyprus, Poland, and Belgium. The comparative analysis in the paper demonstrates that all jurisdictions share similarities in managing conflicts of interest in private companies, such as the obligation of company officers to disclose conflicts. However, there are some differences in liability for non-disclosure and the regulation of related party transactions. The paper offers recommendations based on this comparative analysis.

Keywords: conflict of interest, private company, related party transaction.

1. Introduction

Conflicts of interest in corporate governance occur when a manager, director, or shareholder acts in their own interest or in favour of their related parties, despite their obligation to prioritise the company's interests. Common examples of such conflicts include situations where a director steals the company's secrets or other business opportunities, or where a controlling shareholder extracts wealth from the company through tunnelling via related party transactions. In all these cases, corporate insiders (directors and shareholders) exploit their positions for personal gain, often at the expense of their company and other stakeholders. These conflicts can arise in both private and public companies. Therefore, to balance the interests of stakeholders in companies, national legislators must propose adequate solutions.

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This paper examines the regulation of conflicts of interest in a Ukrainian private company (tovarystvo z obmezhenoyu vidpovidalnistiu, or TOV) through a comparative analysis with the national laws of Cyprus, Poland, and Belgium. These three EU jurisdictions offer valuable insights due to their diverse legal traditions, which encompass both common law and civil law systems. Using a comparative approach, this paper seeks to identify commonalities and differences in how conflicts of interest are addressed within corporate law across various countries, to identify gaps in legal regulation, and to suggest improvements for the legislation of these jurisdictions.

The next section of the paper offers an overview of the legal regulation of conflicts of interest in private companies in Ukraine. Section 3 examines the features of Ukrainian laws in a comparative context with those of three EU Member States: Cyprus, Belgium, and Poland. The final section concludes the paper by summarising the similarities and differences across jurisdictions, and by outlining recommendations for the future development of law in this area.

2. Regulation of Conflicts of Interest in Ukrainian Private Companies

Ukrainian law on private companies (the Law of Ukraine ‘On Limited Liability Companies’, or Ukraine’s LLC Law) contains the definition of the conflict of interest. It is defined as a conflict between the duty of a corporate officer to act reasonably and in good faith in the interest of a company, and the private interests of the company officer or the officer’s affiliated persons.² The law stipulates that a conflict of interest exists even when persons affiliated with company officers receive payments, remuneration, or other benefits from third parties in exchange for actions or inactions related to the performance of the company officers’ duties.³ A company officer who becomes aware of a conflict of interest must inform the company’s management body and the supervisory board (if present) in writing within two days. Once the management board has received this information, it must notify all shareholders of it within two days.⁴ If a company officer fails to disclose a conflict of interest to the company, they may be dismissed without compensation.⁵

By extending the effect of a conflict of interest to situations where an officer’s affiliated person transacts with the company, the statute recognises the concept of an indirect conflict of interest.⁶ Among

² Law of Ukraine ‘On Limited Liability Companies’, No. 2275-VIII, from 6 February 2018, Article 42(3).

³ Ibid, Article 42(5).

⁴ Ibid, Article 42(6).

⁵ Ibid, Article 42(8).

⁶ Romashchenko I., *Related Party Transactions and Corporate Groups: When Eastern Europe Meets the West*, Kluwer Law International 2020, p. 80.

other things, this type of conflict of interest is also found in Dutch jurisprudence and legislation. According to the 2007 decision of the Supreme Court of the Netherlands in the *Bruil/Combex* case, the director could be viewed as having conflicting interests if due to the existence of a personal interest or through his involvement with another interest that is not concurrent with that of the legal entity, the director must be deemed incapable of safeguarding the interests of the company and its business in a manner that may be expected from a trustworthy and unprejudiced director.⁷ In the same year, 2007, the Supreme Court of the Netherlands, in the *Versatel* case, prohibited both management and supervisory board members from participating in deliberations and decision-making in cases of indirect conflict of interest.⁸ Now this rule can be found in the statute.⁹

An essential aspect of the concept of indirect conflict of interest under Ukrainian law for private companies is the idea of an affiliated party. For the definition of an affiliated party, the Ukrainian LLC Law refers to the law on public companies, which is the Law of Ukraine ‘On Joint Stock Companies’.¹⁰ The latter act recognises two types of individuals who can be linked to a natural person: either the person’s family members, including spouses, parents, guardians, brothers, sisters, children and their spouses, and/or a legal entity controlled by that individual.¹¹ A company officer must submit a list of affiliated persons to the company and update the company on any changes within five days after the change occurs.¹² Therefore, whenever an officer’s affiliated party enters into a transaction with the officer’s company, it may trigger the officer’s obligation to disclose the conflict of interest to the company. Of course, for a transaction to involve a conflict of interest, it must still be related to the performance of the officer’s duties. However, the officer may not necessarily be aware of the transaction between the affiliated person and a third party. And even if he is aware of it, it would still be questionable whether it relates to the officer's duties. Therefore, the officer might fail to disclose this conflict of interest promptly and face the negative consequences as prescribed by law. This issue has been previously discussed in the literature, and it has been suggested that the duty to disclose conflicts of interest should

⁷ Bruil/Combex, 29 June 2007, JOR 2007/169 (Supreme Court of the Netherlands).

⁸ Versatel, Decision of 14 September 2007 NJ 2007, 612 (Supreme Court of the Netherlands).

⁹ Civil Code of the Netherlands (Burgelijk Wetboek), Articles 2:239(6), 2:250(5).

¹⁰ Law of Ukraine ‘On Limited Liability Companies’, Article 42(9).

¹¹ Law of Ukraine ‘On Joint Stock Companies’, No. 2465-IX, from 27 July 2022, Article 2(1)(1).

¹² Law of Ukraine ‘On Limited Liability Companies’, Article 42(4).

be triggered when the transaction could cause harm to the company, as some transactions between affiliated persons and third parties may benefit the company.¹³

In addition to the stated rules, Ukraine's LLC Law bans company officers from accepting any benefits outside of those specified in their contract with the company and from revealing confidential company information.¹⁴ Company officers (members of the management and supervisory boards) are also prohibited from competing with the company by engaging in activities within the same area as the company where they are employed, unless they obtain approval for these actions from the relevant corporate bodies.¹⁵ Failure to adhere to these requirements will result in the company's right to dismiss the officer without compensation.¹⁶ Members of the management board and the supervisory board are also liable to the company for any damages they cause.¹⁷

Finally, Ukraine's LLC Law includes optional provisions on approval safeguards for related party transactions: shareholders can incorporate provisions mandating the approval of self-transactions. These provisions must be approved by all shareholders in a company and integrated into the company's articles of association to take effect.¹⁸ In other words, Ukrainian law not only makes the approval process for related party transactions optional; it also sets a high threshold for shareholders to implement it – instead of a majority approval, the law requires unanimous consent from all shareholders. This approach to regulation decreases the likelihood of personalised requirements for approving related party transactions being enforced in Ukrainian private companies, as it is unlikely that all shareholders would agree to these requirements within a company.

3. Comparative Observations from Cyprus, Belgium, and Poland

¹³ Romashchenko I., *Related Party Transactions and Corporate Groups*, p. 81; Romashchenko I.O. *Vdoskonalennia korporatyvnoho zakonodavstva pro konflikt interesiv. Rekodyfikatsiia Tsyvilnoho Kodeksu Ukrainy: perspektyvy pravovoho rehuliuвання korporatyvnykh vidnosyn [text]: Collection of scientific works of the XIX International Scientific Conference (24 September 2021, Ivano-Frankivsk) / F. H. Burchak Research Institute of Private Law and Entrepreneurship of the National Academy of Legal Sciences of Ukraine; Edited by V. A. Vasyliieva. Ivano-Frankivsk, 2021. P. 119.*

¹⁴ Law of Ukraine 'On Limited Liability Companies', Article 42 (2,7).

¹⁵ *Ibid*, Article 40(5).

¹⁶ *Ibid*, Article 42 (8).

¹⁷ *Ibid*, Article 40(2).

¹⁸ *Ibid*, Article 45.

This paper discusses the following business forms of entrepreneurial entities in the context of Cyprus, Poland, and Belgium: the private company limited by shares (Ltd.) in Cyprus, the limited liability company (sp. z o.o.) in Poland, and the private company (BV/SRL) in Belgium.

Similarly to Ukraine, in Cyprus, Belgium, and Poland, directors or managers must inform the company of any conflicts of interest they may have in transactions they intend to enter into.¹⁹ The procedures and consequences of breaching this duty differ considerably. In Cyprus, the director must inform the board or face a fine for failing to meet this requirement.²⁰ Poland does not impose particular liabilities on management board members who fail to disclose conflicts of interest to the board. However, if this omission causes harm to the company, it could lead to a liability lawsuit against the management board member.²¹ In Belgium, a director's failure to disclose a conflict of interest to other directors or to the management body (if established) can result in the nullification of a transaction.²² If damages occur, it can also lead to a liability lawsuit against the director who gained an unlawful financial advantage at the company's detriment.²³ In Ukraine, if company officers cause damage by breaching conflict of interest rules, they can also be held liable for the resulting damages.²⁴ However, what is more important from a practical perspective is that these actions serve as grounds for their dismissal without compensation.²⁵ Due to labour law limitations in Ukraine that protect employees' rights, including those of managers and directors, this provision serves as a helpful tool for shareholders seeking to dismiss a breaching director more quickly. Moreover, an interesting distinction between the notification obligations in the three countries previously mentioned and Ukraine is the presence of a two-day notification period in Ukraine. It seems other countries could adopt this regulatory feature, as it provides greater clarity and detail on how directors should disclose their conflicts of interest.

In addition to their general notification duty, all three jurisdictions specify particular procedural requirements for transactions involving directors or related parties. Under traditional English case law,

¹⁹ This duty is not explicitly mentioned in Poland. Still, it is implied, as members of the management board must refrain from participating in deliberations on issues where they have a conflict of interest. See Polish Code of Commercial Companies (Kodeks spółek handlowych, or KSH), Article 209.

²⁰ The Companies Law of the Republic of Cyprus, Cap 113, section 191(1).

²¹ KSH, Article 293(1).

²² Belgian Companies Code, Article 5:77.

²³ *Ibid*, Article 5:78.

²⁴ Law of Ukraine 'On Limited Liability Companies', Article 40(2).

²⁵ *Ibid*, Articles 40(6), 42(8).

applicable in Cyprus, self-interested transactions by directors are typically prohibited²⁶ but may be validated with the approval of the shareholders.²⁷ In contrast, Poland only necessitates approval from the general meeting of shareholders for specific high-risk transactions such as credit, loans, suretyships, and similar agreements.²⁸ For other transactions, the conflicted director must abstain from participating in management board deliberations. The supervisory board is then tasked with representing the company in dealings with the manager.²⁹ Perhaps the most comprehensive regulation is in Belgium, where a director must abstain from discussions when a conflict of interest occurs. If all directors are either interested or absent, the general meeting has the competence to approve the transaction.³⁰ This rule allows reasonable exceptions for companies where the sole shareholder is also the sole director, for intra-group related party transactions, and for transactions carried out in the normal course of business under typical market conditions.³¹ Interestingly, in Ukrainian private companies, rules on transactions between the company and an interested person, including company officers and shareholders with at least 20 per cent of share capital,³² are entirely optional. Moreover, to introduce the approval requirement in the articles of association, all shareholders must give their consent to this.³³ Considering these statutory requirements, it is unlikely that rules on related party transactions would be included in the articles of private companies. This regulatory approach aligns with the current concentration of capital in private companies, where the sole shareholder often manages the company. However, in the case of private companies in Ukraine, where managers and directors are not connected to shareholders, it is worth exploring the introduction of mandatory procedural safeguards for self-interested transactions involving directors or their related parties. For example, managers or directors might be required to abstain from participating in discussions within the corporate bodies of private companies, unless specific exceptions apply, as seen in Belgian company law.

4. Conclusion

²⁶ See: *Aberdeen Railway Co v Blaikie Bros* (1854) 1 Macq 461.

²⁷ See: *North West Transportation Co Ltd v Beatty* (1887) 12 App Cas 589.

²⁸ KSH, Article 15(1).

²⁹ *Ibid*, Article 210(1).

³⁰ Belgian Companies Code, Article 5:76(1), (2), (3).

³¹ *Ibid*, Article 5:76(4), (5).

³² Law of Ukraine 'On Limited Liability Companies', Article 45(1,3).

³³ *Ibid*, Article 45(2).

Both the Ukrainian law on private companies and the laws of selected jurisdictions, Cyprus, Poland, and Belgium, contain provisions addressing conflicts of interest of company officers.

A common feature of the laws in all these countries is the requirement for company officers to disclose their conflicts of interest to the company. Failure to inform the company by a company officer can lead to negative consequences; for example, in Cyprus, it results in a fine for a director. In Ukrainian private companies, company officers who fail to disclose their conflicts of interest can be dismissed without compensation, which serves as a helpful remedy for shareholders. One aspect of Ukrainian company law that other countries might adopt is the two-day period for a company officer to notify conflicts of interest.

Regarding the rules on related party transactions in private companies, Ukraine has a distinctive regulatory approach, as the regulations concerning transactions with interested persons can only be enforced if all shareholders of the company agree to them. Meanwhile, Cyprus, Poland, and Belgium provide mandatory procedural safeguards for self-interested transactions, such as approval by a corporate body and/or the abstention of an interested person from participating in the deliberations of that corporate body. Therefore, it seems that in this area, Ukraine could benefit from the experience of these jurisdictions and introduce specific mandatory requirements for managers and directors in private companies, such as a duty to abstain from discussions in corporate bodies unless exceptions apply, including one-person companies, intra-group transactions, and transactions conducted in the ordinary course of business and on standard market terms.

1. *Aberdeen Railway Co v Blaikie Bros (1854) 1 Macq 461.*
2. *Belgian Companies Code, from 4 April 2019. Available at: https://www.ejustice.just.fgov.be/cgi_loi/change_lg.pl?language=fr&la=F&cn=2019032309 (accessed on 07/09/2025).*
3. *Bruil/Combex, 29 June 2007, JOR 2007/169 (Supreme Court of the Netherlands).*
4. *Civil Code of the Netherlands (Burgelijk Wetboek). Available at: <https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0003045/2025-01-01> (accessed on 07/09/2025).*
5. *Law of Ukraine 'On Limited Liability Companies', No. 2275-VIII, from 6 February 2018. Available at: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2275-19> (accessed on 07/09/2025).*
6. *Law of Ukraine 'On Joint Stock Companies', No. 2465-IX, from 27 July 2022. Available at: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2465-20> (accessed on 07/09/2025).*
7. *North West Transportation Co Ltd v Beatty (1887) 12 App Cas 589.*

8. *Polish Code of Commercial Companies (Kodeks spółek handlowych)*. Available at: <https://isap.sejm.gov.pl/isap.nsf/download.xsp/WDU20000941037/U/D20001037Lj.pdf> (accessed on 07/09/2025).

9. *Romashchenko I. Related Party Transactions and Corporate Groups: When Eastern Europe Meets the West*, Kluwer Law International 2020.

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11. *The Companies Law of the Republic of Cyprus, Cap 113*. Available at: <http://www.cylaw.org/nomoi/arith/CAP113.pdf> (accessed on 07/09/2025).

12. *Versatel, Decision of 14 September 2007 NJ 2007, 612 (Supreme Court of the Netherlands)*.